

Intellectual Imperialism in Nigerian Universities and the Imperativeness of Decolonizing Education

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Abstract

This paper explores the complex dynamics surrounding the continuation of Western epistemologies within African educational systems, with a specific focus on Nigerian universities. By drawing from scholarly discourse and personal experiences, the study sheds light on the ongoing struggle to incorporate indigenous knowledge systems into the fabric of knowledge production. It examines the historical roots of this issue, tracing it back to colonialism and the establishment of educational structures designed to serve colonial interests. Using the lens of intellectual imperialism, as conceptualized by Syed Hussein Alatas, the paper analyses the exploitation of local knowledge and the marginalization of indigenous epistemologies in favour of Western methodologies. The paper also explores the lasting impact of neoliberal reforms, which have worsened the marginalization of education in Nigeria. The paper highlights the consequences of intellectual alienation, including the production of non-progressive knowledge and the perpetuation of ideological biases. It also touches upon issues of academic practice, such as citation practices, which reinforce the dominance of Western scholarship. Ultimately, the study calls for concerted efforts to decolonize education and promote the localization of knowledge production, thus paving the way for genuine societal development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Decolonization, Intellectual Imperialism, Knowledge Production, Nigerian Universities.

Introduction

The relatively hegemonic status of Western methodologies and epistemic systems in African educational systems constitutes a topic of animated ideological discourse among scholars of knowledge production in Africa. Lee (2013) has accurately observed that such discussions continue to proceed as footnotes within the larger discourse of the need to incorporate autochthonous epistemological systems as the basis of all knowledge produced, which, in other words, is an attempt to address the flaws noted by Mazrui when he contended that "*what Africa*

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knows about itself and what different parts of Africa know about each other has been profoundly influenced by the West" (Mazrui, 1986:13). This attempt to rescue is an up growth of a long tradition of thought that began with the contributions of cerebral scholars such as Claude Ake and Syed Alatas.

As far as the various readings of the works attributed to this duo go, they were essentially organized around the objective of delinking the theoretical and empirical core of higher education in Africa from alien influences to reflect the demands of the local environments within which such institutions are situated. Basically, such attempts aspired towards a reversal of an unfortunate dynamic where African institutions of learning function as mere satellites of Western intellectualism, with its attendant mindless importation of Western ideological values and objectives without recourse to the domestic environments of the locales where such institutions are domiciled (Amusan, 2016).

However, cumulative anecdotal evidence from the numerous critiques produced by Nigerian universities in recent times and testimonies of students attests to the general failure of this message to reflect practically in the curriculum and practice of education in Nigeria. The alienation from the environment that social science disciplines continue to experience is doubly harmful and one dynamic that must be reversed to set off the continent's development efforts. On the back of the modest nature of the gains made, it is especially curious to understand the underlying factors of the continued alienation of the social sciences. To that end, that puzzle and the related objective of mapping the dynamics and processes by which alienation is produced constitute the two primary lines of inquiry for this paper. In pursuing these lines of inquiry, we draw on experiences within the academic world while making keen use of Syed Alatas' construct of 'intellectual imperialism' as the conceptual framework. These experiences have exposed us to different manifestations of the colonization of knowledge production and informed our decision to reflect on the alienated nature of knowledge production fully. In developing and emphasizing its arguments, the paper progresses as a one-part discourse broken into seven sub-sections.

In the first section, we clarify the concept of intellectual imperialism. In this section, we delve into the concept of intellectual imperialism within African educational systems, particularly focusing on Nigerian universities. Drawing from Syed Hussein Alatas' work, we define intellectual imperialism and highlight the detrimental effects of intellectual imperialism, including identity loss and the distortion of psycho-cultural systems, emphasizing the urgent need for decolonizing education and promoting the localization of knowledge production processes to foster genuine societal development.

In the second part, we delve into colonialism's broader effects on indigenous identities and cultural practices, highlighting the repression of indigenous customs and traditions in favor of European ideals. Thereafter, we explore the colonial origins of Nigerian universities and their enduring influence on educational structures and philosophies. Among many other things, we trace the development of university education in Nigeria from the efforts of colonial administration, highlighting how universities were designed to serve colonial interests by producing personnel and resources to sustain colonial structures. This is followed by a discussion of the contributing roles of government policy, focusing on neoliberal reforms implemented in the 1980s. We demonstrate that these policies led to declines in academic

research output, exacerbating the challenges faced by Nigerian universities and hindering their ability to become first-class institutions. Thereafter, we turn our gaze to discussing the pervasive influence of colonial and neoliberal ideologies on Nigerian universities, particularly concerning academic practices and intellectual culture. We critique indigenous contributions to the lingering reverence for Western epistemologies and the reinforcement of the dominance of whiteness in academic discourse and knowledge production. In the next section, we ponder on the profound consequences of the ongoing alienation of Nigerian universities stemming from the legacies of colonialism and post-colonial dynamics, after which we conclude and summarize.

Understanding intellectual imperialism

Any discussion within the field, such as where this work is situated, must inevitably take cognizance of several terms. Chief among such terms is the notion of intellectual imperialism. To fully contextualize this notion, one must refer to Syed Hussein Alatas' 2000 article "*Intellectual Imperialism: Definition, Traits, and Problems*". In that article, Alatas (2000) discusses intellectual imperialism as a notion that deserves much more than the attention it gets, given its serious character. In terms of definition, intellectual imperialism is shown to be a concatenation of the usual properties of imperialism. Consequently, from his expositions, intellectual imperialism retains an exploitative dimension: the expropriation of local knowledge for the pernicious purpose of reconstructing local narratives to project images modelled after the agenda of foreign agents. This dynamic, which proceeds in the same fashion as the extraction-export-processing-and-reimportation model, which was in vogue during the colonialist era, contributes to a distorted knowledge economy advantageous economically for foreign publishers and economies. Societies are not active incubators of knowledge but rather a source of intellectual raw materials that are aggregated into "the books which would be exported back to the country of fieldwork" (Alatas, 2000: 33-34). In this state, such societies cannot set the rules and dictate research conventions but are recipients of received wisdom.

From a standpoint, intellectual imperialism corresponds to an economic, political, and psychological phenomenon that reproduces an unequal knowledge economy relationship that places institutions from the Global South as subalterns and satellites of epistemic and methodological systems originating from the Global South. This dynamic finds a succinct illustration in Mazrui's contention that Africa's identity and shared memories are externally derived and determined rather than emergent constructs of indigenous efforts (Mazrui, 1986; Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2014). Intellectual imperialism begets a sense of identity loss and crises, which finds expression at micro and macro levels. This derives from the fact that it reconstructs the psycho-cultural systems of individuals and societies.

Essentially, intellectual imperialism stands as a powerful antithesis to the localization of knowledge, or what has been termed as "endogeneity in knowledge production," in the Claude Ake formulation (Jeremiah, 2008). It disregards the 'historical ecological outlay' of the locale within which such knowledge about social reality is produced and enables the hegemonic status of alien knowledge production systems (Ake, 1986; Jeremiah, 2008). This begets a situation where the researcher cannot present anything other than vulgar knowledge that betrays the very character of genuinely derived knowledge, which, according to Ake (1986: i),

should be “the summation of the existential realities of social life and its developmental possibilities.”

The crisis of indigenous relevance and identity complications facing universities irreconcilably express the manifestations of dynamics associated primarily with the activities of colonialism. In its basic expression, colonialism operated a system defined by an intrinsically dominative, exploitative, and control dimension. These ideals were keenly visible in several policies, such as the indirect rule policy pursued vigorously by Lord Lugard and described in the extract below:

“The focus was on rural communities or tribal units as a mechanism for stabilizing colonial society in order to prevent what was referred to as the immanent “breakdown” of traditional society with the erosion of customs and traditions that were held to provide for social cohesion. That search for stability was linked to notions of population decline, the dangers of urbanization and the rise of a class of “detrribalized” subjects who would pose a threat not only to the traditional tribal order but to the colonial order itself where African nationalism was emerging as a significant force.” (Kallaway, 2020:8)

Essentially, colonialism amounted to the perpetuation of psychological and cultural violence, wherein there was drastic repression and suppression of the indigenous identities in favor of a superficial image that advanced the goals of the colonialists, resulting ultimately in the devaluation of Africans for the sake of glorification of Europe (Nyamnjoh, 2012). Essentially, this substitution of identities legitimized the colonial structures and created apologists for colonial authority. As p’Bitek (1989) demonstrates, men and women educated by the colonialists were transformed into ‘subjects’ incapable of objecting to the authority of the colonialists in a critical fashion, which could be directly linked to the desires of the latter to command power without accountability to the people over whom this power was exercised.

The colonial origins of universities

In assessing Nigerian universities sustained, unchanging character, it is necessary to commence with an anthropological exploration of their origins. University education proceeded from the efforts of colonial administration and reflected the colonialists' ideo-philosophical worldview. Effectively, as has been historicized, universities were nurseries of personnel and resources required to sustain the colonial structure.

According to Azu (1976), universities were designed to meet colonial manpower needs and protect colonial economic interests from competition emerging from indigenous spheres. The competitive dimension of the dynamic described beforehand is captured poignantly as follows: “they did not want to stimulate into existence an African industrial bourgeoisie who might someday compete against the European bourgeoisie” (Azu, 1976: 328). Importantly too, educational institutions amounted to mechanisms for the attainment of alienation of natives from original cultural and psychological environments into alternative psycho-cultural environments envisioned by the colonialists (Adebisi, 2014).

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Indeed, this point is visible in the circumstances surrounding the formation of the Yaba Higher College, which is considered the watershed in Nigeria's university education history. This institution emblemized the deliberately skewed nature of the philosophy and practice of colonial education. Capturing this poignantly,

“YHC was heavily criticised for subjecting its candidates to substandard curricula which were meant to produce subordinate officers to the European expatriates who supervised the programmes and their products. Again, each programme was to last six to seven years, about twice the length of time a person needed to graduate from a first degree university course, and almost twice the length of time used by their European bosses to graduate” (Oyebade and Dike, 318-319).

As is evident in the foregone account and testimony from the literature, the alienation of universities from indigenous contexts cannot be adequately explained independently of the political economy of colonialism. Analysed within this analytical frame, the defective character of institutions of knowledge production owed more to the necessities and dynamics triggered by the evolution of capitalist philosophy of imperialism. Such factors were produced by structural reformulations of the socio-economic systems in Europe, which produced a few exigencies that were to be satisfied through the tweaking of knowledge production systems and techniques. According to Ake (1984:616):

“In the wake of the process of primitive accumulation which preceded the Industrial Revolution, there was a serious problem of controlling behaviour, of finding adequate ideological representations of the emerging mode of production. First, masses of people had to be dislodged from pre-capitalist production relations and expropriated, then they had to be dissuaded from occupying themselves in unproductive ways such as begging and induced to offer their labour power as a commodity. The foundations of contemporary social sciences were laid in the context of these problems and grew in step with the development of industrial capitalism.”

Furthermore, as Rodney (1972) also illustrates, the colonial bias in forming the university system consequently fomented the institution of quantitative limitations that circumscribe the quality and content of such systems implemented. In that respect, it is thus unsurprising that the dominant tendency of universities thus became a matter of the uncritical absorption and glorification of “*every bit of wonder out of the West*,” as Azu (1976) puts it, as the benchmark and gold standard of intellectualization within the walls of universities. This could not be unconnected with the Eurocentric worldview espoused by the colonialists that discussed indigenous identities and constitutive elements in a patronizing fashion, which advanced a picture of inequality in character. In the Eurocentric thought, Africans were highlighted as villains: irrational, unproductive, un-progressive, despotic, and barbaric- ideals antithetical to the supposed properties of European ideological and epistemic systems (Onwuzuruigbo, 2014).

With this came the emergence of rigid conservativeness, which is as so captured quaintly by Ashby (1966: 246-247):

“Some African intellectuals, especially those educated in Britain, resist changes in curriculum or in pattern of courses because they confuse such changes with a lowering of standards. They are accordingly suspicious of any divergence from the British pattern. Some of them are particularly allergic to proposals for incorporating African Studies into the curriculum”.

Implicitly, by so doing, the institutions and personnel employed entered service as powerful guardians of the colonial rear-guard. Invariably, this colonial bias conditioned institutions and structures of education to reflect objectives and skewed values which rendered them environmentally irrelevant and dysfunctional, which replicates pseudo-intellectual objectives. According to Nyamnjoh (2012):

“The epistemology has resulted in social science disciplines and fields of study that have sacrificed morality, humanity and the social on the altar of a conscious or implied objectivity that is at best phoney. It has allowed the insensitivities of power and comfort to assume the moral high ground, dictating to the marginalized and the disabled, and preaching salvation and promising ‘development’ for individuals and groups who repent from ‘retrogressive’ attitudes, cultures, traditions and practices. As an epistemology that claims the status of a solution, there is little room for introspection or self-scrutiny. Countervailing forces are invariably to blame for ‘failure’. Such messianic qualities have imbued practitioners of this epistemology with an attitude of arrogance, superiority and intolerance towards creative difference and appropriation. Its evangelical zeal to convert creative difference has not excluded resorting to violence, for the epistemology knows neither compromise nor negotiation, nor conviviality.”

Defunding of universities

Whatever prospects of reversing this insalubrious condition existed were effectively quashed with the wave of neoliberal restructuring reforms that came into play in the late 20th century. These reforms, also known as Structural Adjustment Programs, arose out of the need to reconcile economic issues in Third World countries. Such programs emerged as a product of a three-way collaboration involving state governments and the twin financial institutions of the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (Ekpo, 2017).

According to Ekpo (2017), Structural Adjustment Programs were corrective in objectives and orientated toward the attainment of a sustainable aggregate demand-supply balance, production expansion, and the effacement of balance-of-payment constraints. To that end, various policies and strategies were integrated into state policy and became a defining feature of state behavior.

The implementation of these policies and programs excited considerable pushback from within the civil society on account of their devastating consequences, which have been summarized by Bangura (1986) to have manifested in the form of the depression of living conditions of the poor people through changes in domestic incomes and prices as well as the creation of a semblance of balance in domestic and foreign accounts at the expense of basic social services. The massive slump in living conditions was coterminous with a raft of depressing changes set off within the education system.

According to one account: the educational system was deregulated, and this apart from effecting crunching job losses, was responsible for *meteoric* hikes in school fees which triggered significant disruptions felt from primary education to secondary and university levels (Danladi & Nankieel, 2016). Unsurprisingly, the impact on the education system also materialised through significant cuts to education funding. Such cuts were visibly illustrated in the dataset constructed by Babalola, Lungwangwa and Adeyinka (1999) and illustrated in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: % of public budget expenditure on education during the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in Nigeria (1981-1988).

Source: Babalola, Lungwangwa and Adeyinka (1999).

Within a 7-year period from 1981-1988, public expenditure on education plummeted from a respectable 7.8% in 1981 to a meagre 2% in 1988. Notably, such drastic cuts shared common spaces with a redirection of priorities and agendas within Nigerian higher education, which was captured succinctly in remarks such as that credited to Donald Ekong that attested to the fact that African universities experienced economically induced declines in academic research output, resulting in the extinction of aspirations for the emergence of first-class institutions (Ekong, 1991 in Godonoo).

Whiteness and Anti-Indigenous Bias

In the current dispensation, the trends set off by the periods of colonial administration and neo-liberal restructuring have remained indelible markers of the current paradigm of thought and

behaviour within Nigerian universities. The preserving and enduring character of this dynamic has emanated solely from the activities of intellectuals. Writing at the turn of the 21st century, Iyela (2001:207) made the following comments:

“No conference paper presented by them is considered erudite enough unless it produces a long list of references of works of white scholars. Even when his Nigerian counterpart has done a substantial work in the area he is writing on, there are many Nigerian intellectuals who find it more convenient to cite or quote from the works of white scholars no matter how irrelevant they are to our circumstance.”

Iyela’s comments highlight a phenomenon evident in academic circles, where scholars from certain backgrounds or regions feel compelled to reference works by scholars from dominant or Western cultures, even when comparable or relevant work has been done by scholars from their own culture or region. This behaviour can be seen as an example of academic imperialism and reflects a bias towards Eurocentric perspectives in the academia. This tendency suggests that some scholars prioritize citing or referencing works by white scholars, even if they are not directly applicable to their own cultural or societal context. This pattern of behaviour can perpetuate a cycle of marginalization and underrepresentation of non-Western perspectives in academic discourse.

The Dangers of Alienation

The ultimate consequence of the perpetuation of the alienation of Nigerian universities, occasioned by the dynamics of colonialism and post-colonialism, is captured succinctly by Ake’s description of social science-society relations which he captured in the following terms: “Since the social sciences are largely the product of very narrow interests tendentially in fundamental conflict with the rest of society, they tend to be ideological representations rather than tools of scientific understanding”(Ake, 1984:621). Additionally, there is a perpetuation of parochial thought paradigms and the production of non-progressive knowledge, which incentivises paucity of “basic research of an open-ended nature that questions fundamental assumptions of existing social science practice” (Ake, 1984: 622).

Ake’s assessment of the consequences of alienation in Nigerian universities makes several profound observations. It suggests that ‘veritable knowledge’ production at the social sciences have been shaped by narrow interests which are often in contradiction with broad social goals and objectives, which make them ideological and pseudo-scientific. Research in that field has consequently not been driven by the desire to foster the production of ‘veritable knowledge’ but by the need to serve agendas. Consequently, this has resulted in perpetuating parochial thought paradigms and the continuous production of non-progressive knowledge. Consequently, it becomes impossible for a culture of innovation to thrive. With its roots in historical and systemic dynamics created by colonialism, the consequent condition has prompted the development of largely ‘luxurious, socially meaningless’ knowledge incapable of contributing to societal progress.

Concluding Notes

The delocalization of knowledge production has created a very flawed dynamic that needs to be fixed. To address this shortcoming, it is critical to implement strategies that prioritize funding regional research projects as a fundamental tenet of academic culture and policy. These solutions could seek to promote and fund socially relevant research that addresses societal needs and issues, with a focus on funding socially impactful projects from a financial pool that might arise from the combined efforts of Nigeria's publicly and privately funded universities. Facilitating open-access publishing and collaboration among Nigerian scholars who live locally and abroad should also be a priority in achieving this. This can encourage the generation of forward-thinking knowledge and enable the interchange of ideas.

However, such actions would not advance unless they come after changes that guarantee higher levels of institutional autonomy for Nigerian universities. This autonomy would guarantee that the universities maintain control over the development and shaping of research agendas and are shielded from excessive political influence, promoting an environment of academic freedom and intellectual independence. Coordination between the government, academic institutions, civil society organizations, and foreign partners is necessary to implement these proposals. Nigerian universities may contribute more to knowledge advancement and societal advancement by tackling the underlying reasons of alienation and fostering a culture of rigorous inquiry and societal involvement.

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